

ReNEW

Generic applications deployment to the
Living Labs v2

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification Systems
API	Application Programming Interface
D	Deliverable
DNS	Domain Name System
DS	Data Space
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EURIS	European River Information Services System
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GA	Grant Agreement
GraphQL	Graph Query Language
GUI	General User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
IDP	Identity Provider
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWT-DT	Inland Waterway Transport Digital Twin
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LDES	linked Data Event Streams
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OSS	Open-Source Software
REST	Representational State Transfer
RH SSO	Red Hat Single Sign-On
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SSH	Secure Shell
SSO	Single Sign-On
ST	Sub-task
UI	User Interface
VM(s)	Virtual Machine(s)
WP	Work Package(s)

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1 Executive Summary

ReNEW is the acronym for the project "Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways". This project is funded by the European Commission under the topic "HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-09 "Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways".

The objective of the ReNEW project is to drive economic growth while minimizing the sector's negative impact on the environment. To achieve this goal, we are working on the implementation of a data space and digital twin solutions hosted through a digital twin platform that meets the requirements. This platform will be used to provide Living Labs solutions for resilience and sustainability in inland waterways across the European Union.

This document describes the methodology used, the requirements definition, the architecture of the digital twin platform and the deployment method. Requirements for the digital matching platform have been listed for the ReNEW project. Several types have been identified, for example those relating to the Living Labs, digital twin applications, data spaces, and functional and non-functional. They have been collected from inputs provided by our partners in WP1 and WP3. This involves capturing the requirements expressed by the living labs through use cases and technical requirements from the perspective of digital twin and data spaces.

The architecture of the digital twin platform is made up of several functional elements called building blocks. These building blocks are responsible for hosting digital twins, interfacing with data sources, and supporting user applications. The ReNEW digital twin platform is documented and provides a detailed description of its framework, architecture, and deployment method, including the building blocks and interfaces. The technical implementation recommendations, such as utilizing cloud computing and Microsoft Azure, Keycloak, Apache APISIX, and the deployment process on Azure, are explained in detail. The process includes instantiating the ReNEW digital twin platform and deploying it in the Living Labs.

2 Introduction

The ReNEW project aims to facilitate the transition of Inland Waterways Transport (IWT) to a smart, green, sustainable, and climate-resilient sector.

The four Living labs involved in the ReNEW project have multiple ambitions. Firstly, visualize in real-time the situation of the IWT system, and other modes of transportation such as trucks and trains. Secondly, to make enlightened decisions based on a dedicated decision-making framework. Thirdly, simulate extreme weather events to avoid extensive damage to the infrastructure and the IWT sector in general, to be better prepared as climate change negatively affects this sector's operations.

To meet these ambitions, the work of the technical WP3 consists of developing and implementing a Digital Twin (DT) solution connected to a Data Space (DS) within our LLs.

Digital Twin can represent, emulate, predict, optimize, and control the physical space through real-time connectivity, mapping, analysis, and interaction. When combined with models, data, and services Digital Twin offers solutions for enhancing quality, increasing efficiency, cutting costs, mitigating, and ensuring safety. On the one hand, the data flow will be handled by the Data Space which will enable reliable and secure transmission of data from the physical world to the digital twin, enabling precise visualization of the system in real-time. On the other hand, models will support the decision-making and simulation aspects of the project.

This document is one of the deliverables linked to the WP3 work entitled – “European IWT Data Space and Digital Twin Solutions for Resilience and Sustainability”. This deliverable is the second contribution for task 3.4 – “Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v2”. This deliverable consists of a report revolving around the “First LL deployment”.

This document aims to describe in detail the envisioned Digital Twin Platform that will ultimately be deployed in our Living Labs. We will then discuss the technological choices recommended by AKKODIS before describing the implementation process and deployment steps.

3 Methodology

In this section, we will present the different methods used as references to design the detailed architecture of our Digital Twin Platform.

In the case of digital twins, moving from conceptual and theoretical research to actual implementation and deployment of an operational DT requires a critical element materialized in the form of a Digital Twin Platform. Research on this subject has shown that a comprehensive platform is needed to perform simulation analysis and test verification of digital twin models, data, algorithms, interactions, and other related components [1].

The digital twin platform can be seen in some cases as a development-oriented platform for simplifying developments. However, for ReNEW, we're planning to make it a platform for hosting several bricks, which will make it easier to deploy our solution in the LLs.

3.1 Digital Twin Platform Architecture

To devise the architecture for our upcoming Digital Twin platform, we considered multiple elements such as scalability, computational complexity, edge vs cloud. We considered the LLs need to dispose of a Digital Twin able to show information in real-time and perform simulations scenarios.

To enable efficiency in the real-time monitoring of the envisaged platform, we investigated the possible synergies between Digital Twin technology and the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) paradigm [2]. This approach was previously considered while combining DT with 5G/6G connectivity [3].

MEC is supported by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). It offers application developers and content providers cloud-computing capabilities and an IT service environment at the edge of the network [4].

The Multi-access Edge Computing framework standard proposed by ETSI shows the general entities involved. These can be grouped into system-level, host-level, and network-level entities [5]. The host level includes four blocks the platform, applications, virtualization infrastructure, and management. The system level includes only a management block. Last, the network level includes all the external and local networks (see Figure 1).

The MEC approach is particularly interesting for our project. Firstly, it produces a generic enough architecture that could be implemented in various and non-technological-dependant ways (cloud, on-premises etc.). Secondly, the separation between the management and the hosting functionalities contributes also to the genericity of the architecture while facilitating the maintenance of the platform.

Figure 1: Multi-access Edge Computing Framework

We also considered the makeTwin reference architecture for Digital Twin software platform to devise the architecture of our Digital Twin Platform. This approach meets the demand for a universal digital twin software platform and promotes implementation [1].

The makeTwin platform is composed of ten fundamental functional modes such as twinModelBuilder, twinDataProcessor, twinAlgBuilder, twinIoTConnector, twinInteractor, twinSimulator, twinLibrary, twinVisualization, twinSceneTemplate, and twinAppDeployer (see Figure 2). All those modes might not be of relevance while considering the ReNEW project needs however this sets promising grand rules. This configuration aligns with the characteristics considered essential for our platform. Indeed, the makeTwin platform provides interoperability with features such as configurability, callability, modifiability, and extendibility. It can also interact with various APIs.

MakeTwin is significantly different from MEC, as it enables the development of new digital twins by combining generalist blocks. This approach contains interesting elements on connectivity between the blocks. Also, through the twinAppDeployer we have here a tool designed to facilitate flexible deployment.

Figure 2: Architecture for makeTwin software platform

The makeTwin method is particularly interesting for ReNEW since the realization of our digital twin will be a cooperative activity where partners will contribute to certain bricks unified through the Digital Twin platform.

By combining these two methods, we will propose an architecture of a Digital Twin Platform (see [section 5.2](#)) that meets all the requirements (see [section 4](#)) set by our partners in the ReNEW project.

3.2 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The following table (Table 1) maps the ReNEW’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D3.9 Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v2
First LL deployment report.

Task 3.4 Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs

Ensure that the DT and Data Spaces Architecture, tools and services are deployed to provide LL solutions for Resilience and Sustainability to achieve the best possible impacts.

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST3.4.1 Living Labs Resilience & Sustainability services and applications	<p>1- Provide a basis for the identification and classification DT and data spaces enabled resilience and sustainability enhancement activities, strategies, and decisions within the LL's considering both; daily operation under normal conditions, and performance under extreme events, effectuating a multi-objective optimization approach to be integrated into the decision basis of the LLs.</p> <p>2- Help instantiate and deploy resilience and sustainability quantification services in the LLs.</p> <p>3- Ensure that processes and procedures developed in WP1 will be integrated into the DT architecture available for sustainability a holistic system representation will be facilitated and developed whereby service levels can be benchmarked considering positive correlations between resilience and sustainability.</p> <p>4- Provide guidelines for the deployment of DTs tailored to the resilient and sustainable IWT infrastructure system methodology developed through WP1, including integration within the decision-making process, consideration of the system's current state, and evaluation of performance indicators.</p>	This subtask is developed in section 4 and section 5
ST3.4.2 Autonomous Barge system Digital Twin	<p>1- Design the reference transport system that is used in the assessment of autonomous barge transport. This will include cargo volumes transported between different destinations in the system, including today's transport with trucks that are being transferred to autonomous barges.</p> <p>2- Develop a digital twin of the selected traffic system, including the barges, trucks, and ships that are currently operating in the system and the new autonomous barges that are planned to operate there.</p> <p>3- Relevant infrastructure, such as bridges or locks that have effects on transport will also be modelled.</p>	This subtask is developed in section 4

	<p>4- The digital twin will be used to simulate the autonomous barge transport system and estimate the following parameters: Transport capacity and speed, energy needed for barges and relevant infrastructure, and effects on riverbanks and wildlife from barge traffic.</p>	
<p>ST3.4.3 Deployment to the LLs</p>	<p>1- The development will follow two major cycles, the first including the most important components and services available on M18, and the follow-up and refinement step at M30. 2- The demonstrated solutions implementation will take place in the Living Labs, while the DT, Data Spaces, services, and solutions 'excellence' team will provide support and guidance following a "train the trainer" approach and helping with the technical implementation and coordination of the LL cases. 3- The task will iteratively aggregate outputs of all LL deployments and as new insights emerge, will continually refine, and update the DT and the data spaces to address the needs of the LL stakeholders.</p>	<p>This subtask is developed in section 6</p>

4 Requirements

In this section requirements have been identified and compiled by our partners in WP1 and WP3. Here our aim is to describe the requirements expressed by the living labs with their use cases, while considering technical requirements from the DT, and DS perspective with functional and non-functional aspects.

4.1 Living Labs Requirements

Based on the GA description, this section proposes potential use cases expected from the IWT digital twin to fulfil ReNEW's objectives. It mainly enables capturing the requirement of the system to be designed, and it describes the use cases associated with core services expected from based-resilience IWT-DT.

The oriented diagram in Figure 3 depicts a set of use cases as stated in the GA. A use case represents the behaviour and the capabilities of the IWT-DT in response to a user's request to achieve a given objective. The governing relationship between use cases may be either inclusion when the arrow goes out from the parent to use case towards the child use case, which means the parent use case includes the functionality of the child use case, or extension when the arrow between the child use case and the parent use case points towards the latter which means that the parent use case behaviour may be extended by the child use case.

Some identified use cases are common to all LLs, and others are more specific. Depending on the objectives and desired functionalities, we have identified use cases for simulation, monitoring, planning, analysis, and decision-making support.

Figure 3: IWT-DT use cases Source: IRTX

More details about the use cases depicted in Figure 3 are available in the deliverable D1.8 - ReNEW Methodology Specification for Resilience and Sustainability v1 (Tami, R., Khouadjia, M., Asgari, F., Jović, M., & Duhme, W. 2023). As the diagram has not been the subject of a validation workshop, only the principal branches are developed below.

Following the identification of the different use cases made by our partner IRTX from WP1, in the WP3, our partner IMEC worked on prioritizing those use cases to incorporate them in our future DT solution.

A 'Navigability Planning' use case has been suggested, allowing users to input routes and vessel details for a feasibility check, considering factors like lock and bridge clearances to increase the resilience of the IWT-sector and domain. By approaching it as a common use case and requirement across each living lab, it would ensure re-usability across all regions and improving possible adaptation. Navigability in inland waterway transportation, vital for safe vessel passage and timely delivery, depends on factors like for example water depth, channel width, tranquillity, and absence of obstructions on the main corridors of Europe's IWT-network. Environmental changes, such as adverse climate changes and water level fluctuations, further impact navigability in a negative way.

The second proposed common use case, 'Modality Comparison,' involves inputting origin-destination pairs to assess various transportation modalities, considering factors like duration, speed, environmental impact, and cost. This decision support system aids stakeholders in making informed choices, aligning with sustainability goals.

Both common use cases can be influenced by the autonomous barge modality as well. The first would assess how navigability affects the network and show how autonomous barges and their dimensions would prove a worthy alternative in for example shallow waters. Examples would be the X-Barge of LL4 or the FMP (Floating Modular Platform) of LL1. Secondly, these modes could be compared, within the transport network, with more conventional modes such as trucks, trains and ships equipped with combustion engines.

The technical requirements revolve around Open Local Digital Twins, enhancing capabilities through dataspace connectors. The use cases involve a digital twin ecosystem for inland waterway transport, utilizing dataspace connectors for secure data exchange, ensuring interoperability and a 'split-of-concerns' between different parties from a more architectural & software-design perspective.

Current and future alignment with Living Labs involves integrating specific data from diverse sources that describe the transport system, like APDL's and EuRIS' data on waterways, locks, and bridges, into the reference system. Living Lab 3's route planner intersects with navigability calculations and modality comparison and showcasing promising alignment-potential with the knowledge graph constructed in WP1.

Living Labs 1, 2, and 4 provide rich repositories of data on vessels and barges, serving as input for simulations and scenarios related to the 2 common use cases. This integration ensures practicality, depth, and alignment with the project's overarching objectives without having the risk of executing in disconnected, stand-alone modus (further information are available in D3.2 - Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT) Dataspace and generic Digital Twin Architecture v2).

4.2 Digital Twin Applications Requirements

The table below (Table 2) sets out the digital twin requirements identified by our partner ITA for a seamless integration on the digital twin platform.

Table 2: Digital twin requirements for a digital twin platform

ID	Category	Statement	Required (R) or Optional (O)
DT-R1	IWT digital twin	Initialize the IWT system: This function allows to initialize the IWT system based on the data gathered from the dataspace. It covers the infrastructure, the traffic, the environmental conditions, etc. Once the data is gathered, the DT solution will allow to show the status of the IWT as a whole.	R
DT-R2	IWT digital twin	Evaluate the resilience and sustainability: Based on the data space, the different indicators and KPIs related to the resilience and sustainability of the IWT are calculated and presented in the DT General User Interface (GUI).	R
DT-R3	IWT digital twin	Select risk and vulnerability scenarios: Allows to select the risk and vulnerability scenario based on the proposed catalogue (see D1.2 ¹). For instance, it covers climate change scenarios, cyber security attacks, labour failures, etc.	R
DT-R4	IWT digital twin	Simulate the effect of the scenario: Once the selection of the scenario is done and the parametrization of the DT models is performed, the effect of this scenario on the IWT is simulated at short and long terms.	R
DT-R5	IWT digital twin	Evaluate the effect of the scenario: After the simulation of the impact of the risk and vulnerability scenario, all the indicators and KPI are recalculated and updated to characterize the resilience and sustainability status of the IWT.	R
DT-R6	IWT digital twin	Elaborate mitigation actions: Based on the calculated KPIs, the operator (end-user) has the possibility to fetch actions in order to mitigate the impact of the input scenario on the IWT. Depending on the desired dimension, the operator could ask the digital twin to elaborate and test different strategies to enhance the resilience, sustainability	R

¹ Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v2

ID	Category	Statement	Required (R) or Optional (O)
		or both. It could be at a local or global scale or focused on a category or sub-category of these two dimensions.	
DT-R7	IWT digital twin	Recommend a set of mitigation actions: Once the mitigation actions are elaborated, the decision-making component will sort and present the recommended actions based on the expected KPIs.	R
DT-R8	IWT digital twin	Select and deploy the mitigation action: The operator will select the mitigation action according to his policy. The chosen action is deployed in the DT or in the physical twin if needed.	R
DT-R9	Data access	The DT applications must have access to the ReNEW data space.	R
DT-R10	Data access	The DT applications must have access to the necessary input data (in terms of quantity, quality, format, and trust) to run.	R
DT-R11	Data access	The DT applications must be able to communicate the outputs to the ReNEW data space for further analysis and use.	R
DT-R12	Software	The DT applications must have access to the necessary software, libraries, external tools, or other dependencies to run.	R
DT-R13	Software	The DT applications must be able to communicate with each other (if needed).	R
DT-R14	Software	The DT applications must do its work in a fast, incremental fashion.	R
DT-R15	Software	The DT applications must be able to be updated.	R
DT-R16	Security	The DT applications must be accessed by authorised users only.	R
DT-R17	User interface	The DT applications must be able to be parametrised through a user interface to evaluate different scenarios according to user requirements.	R

4.3 Data Space Requirements

The table below (Table 3) sets out the data space requirements identified by our partner KNT for a seamless integration on the digital twin platform.

Table 3: Data space requirements for a digital twin platform

ID	Category	Statement	Required (R) or Optional (O)
DS-R1	Data access	The ReNEW data space must be accessed through connectors.	R
DS-R2	High-Volume Data Storage	The Data Space must have the capacity to store large volumes of data. This includes geographical information, water flow rates, water levels, weather conditions, and vessel traffic data.	R
DS-R3	Real-Time Data Integration	The ability to integrate real-time data is critical. This includes data from sensors monitoring water levels, flow rates, weather conditions, and vessel movements.	R
DS-R4	Historical Data Storage	For analysis, predictive modelling, and machine learning purposes, storing historical data is important. This includes past weather patterns, water levels, vessel traffic records, and maintenance records.	R
DS-R5	Data Quality and Accuracy	Ensuring high data quality and accuracy is essential for reliable digital twin operations. This involves mechanisms to validate and cleanse data.	R
DS-R6	Security and Privacy Compliance	The Data Space should have robust security protocols to protect sensitive data, especially if it includes information about commercial vessel movements or infrastructure vulnerabilities.	R
DS-R7	Interoperability and Standardization	The ability to integrate with various data sources and formats is crucial. This might involve adhering to certain data standards and protocols to ensure compatibility with external systems.	O
DS-R8	Scalability	The Data Space should be scalable to accommodate increasing amounts of data and more complex analyses as the digital twin evolves.	O
DS-R9	Data Analytics and Processing Capabilities	In addition to storage, the Data Space might need to support analytics and processing functions, enabling the digital twin to perform complex simulations and predictions based on the available data.	O
DS-R10	User Access Management	The system should include mechanisms for managing who can access or modify different types of data, ensuring controlled and authorized use of the information.	O
DS-R11	Backup and Recovery Systems	Reliable backup and recovery solutions are vital to protect data against loss or corruption and ensure the digital twin's continuous operation.	O

4.4 Functional & Non-Functional Requirements

The tables below (Table 4 & Table 5) set out the functional and non-functional requirements identified by our partner IRTX for a seamless integration on the digital twin platform.

Table 4: Functional requirements for a digital twin platform

ID	Category	Statement	Required (R) or Optional (O)
F-R1	Provisioning	The DT platform must provide on-demand compute, memory, and network resources	R
F-R2	Management	The DT platform must provide admin interface to submit requirements for resource provisioning	R
F-R3	Management	The DT platform must provide means to monitor the resources usage	R
F-R4	Interface	The deployed DT must be accessible through a dedicated interface	R
F-R5	Interface	The DT platform must provide interface to external data sources	R
F-R6	Interface	The platform must provide connectors to heterogeneous data sources	R
F-R7	Interface	The platform must harmonize the access to the deployed DT resources	R
F-R8	Security	The platform must follow authorisation rules on the resources provided by the deployed DT	R

Table 5: Non-Functional requirements for a digital twin platform

ID	Category	Statement	Required (R) or Optional (O)
NF-R1	Data protection	Comply the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to protect the users with regard to personal data and the access to it through the dataspace.	R
NF-R2	Latency	The deployed DT must give a response in a given time that could be estimated in a few minutes.	R
NF-R3	Multi-sessions	The deployed DT solution could be used in multi-sessions manner by many users/operators	O

ID	Category	Statement	Required (R) or Optional (O)
NF-R4	Security	The DT platform must implement security mechanisms to ensure the integrity of the hosted software and data	R
NF-R5	Scalability	The DT platform must be able to scale up and down according to the DT applications demand	R
NF-R6	Usability	The DT platform should provide an ergonomic user interface	O
NF-R7	Accessibility	The DT platform must be reachable from its own domain name	R

5 ReNEW Digital Twin Platform

This section details how the ReNEW digital twin platform is designed and what implementation choices are envisaged. Firstly, a framework identifying the general entities involved in the platform's ecosystem is described. Then, from the framework and the requirements provided in [section 4](#), a generic architecture is specified highlighting the proposed building blocks and interfaces. Finally, the technical solutions to implement the main functionalities of the platform are described.

5.1 Framework

The ReNEW digital twin platform allows the deployment of digital twin applications ensuring them access to data sources and providing interface to external applications. It is illustrated in the framework presented in Figure 4 showing the general entities involved which can be grouped into four levels: user, application, digital twin host and data source.

The user level refers to the users interacting through HMIs with applications which rely on insights from the digital twins. They can be the stakeholders from the LL or even public users depending on the applications. It is important to take into account their requirements and the associated user stories as it influences the design and the deployment of the underlining digital twins hence shaping the architecture of the hosting platform.

The application level concerns all the applications getting insights from the digital twins. They require interfaces to receive and send data from and to the digital twins. An example of an application would be a user interface showing a visual representation of the digital twins output data.

The digital host level consists of the following entities:

- The digital twin components hosted by the platform forming the digital twin applications consuming data from the data sources and made available to the users.
- The services offered by the digital twin platform that are necessary for the digital twins' operations e.g., security services, data management etc.
- The virtualisation infrastructure on top of which the digital twin applications and the services are running ensuring reproducibility and scalability among others.
- The digital twin host management which takes care of the management of the platform including the instantiation, the configuration, the monitoring etc.

The data source level groups all the entities responsible for the data input to the hosted digital twins. Example of data sources are data spaces, databases etc.

Figure 4: ReNEW digital twin platform framework

5.2 Architecture

From the framework described in the previous section, a generic architecture has been derived identifying the key functional elements referred as building blocks that comprise the ReNEW digital twin platform as illustrated in Figure 5. Additionally, the architecture highlights the interfaces exposed by the platform to the external entities with respect to the digital twins mainly the data sources and the user applications. The building blocks are grouped into perimeters serving the same functional purposes:

- The digital twin host includes all the building blocks ensuring that the deployed digital twin applications are available and operational
- The management perimeter groups the building blocks managing the platform and the supporting virtualisation infrastructure
- The applications perimeter includes all the user applications interacting with the deployed digital twin applications through the northbound interface
- The data sources perimeter comprises the data producers from which the deployed digital twin applications consume data.

Figure 5: ReNEW digital twin reference architecture

5.3 Building Blocks

5.3.1 DT host

The digital twin host is the perimeter where the digital twin applications are hosted and made available to the user applications. The digital twin host ensures that the deployed digital twin applications are operational by providing computing and memory resources through the virtualisation infrastructure and by hosting supporting services for access and security.

DT core components

In this D3.6 - Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application v1, various assets (models, libraries, etc.) were identified and described. Each of these models serves different purposes, largely covering the functionalities of the components in the WP1 vision of DT components (Figure 6).

Figure 6: WP1 vision of DT components. Source: IRTX.

Furthermore, each model is grounded in specific technology and exhibits varying levels of ambition, with a predominant presence of highly ambitious interactive models based on AnyLogic, Python, HUGIN, Protégé, Neo4j and EuRIS. These models, either already in existence and set for further development, or expected to be developed during the course of the project, are described in detail in section 5 of deliverable D3.6.

The subsequent overview encapsulates the roles, as well as the input and output data prerequisites, associated with each of these models. It is worth noting that both input and output data are expected to be communicated through the ReNEW Data Space. Similarly, the output data must remain accessible for subsequent analysis through a user interface (e.g., a dashboard).

IWT Simulation

- **Role:** The IWT Simulation serves as a virtual model designed to assess resilience in Inland Waterway Transport (IWT).

- **Input:** It expects input data related to the IWT system. This may include information on the network, demand, waterway conditions, vessel capabilities, potential disruptions, and other relevant parameters affecting resilience.
- **Output:** The output from the IWT Simulation includes insights into the system's performance and resilience under various simulated scenarios. This information aids in understanding how the IWT system responds to different challenges.

Process Simulation

- **Role:** The Process Simulation functions as a virtual model specifically focused on evaluating resilience in autonomous operations.
- **Input:** It anticipates input data related to the autonomous operations being simulated. This could involve data on the processes, equipment, environmental conditions, and potential disruptions.
- **Output:** The output consists of insights into the performance and resilience of autonomous operations. This information is crucial for assessing how well the system can adapt and recover from disturbances in a simulated environment.

Bayesian Networks

- **Role:** Bayesian Networks are probabilistic models utilized for assessing the impact on resilience and sustainable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as well as environmental variables.
- **Input:** Bayesian Networks typically require data on variables and their interdependencies. For resilience and sustainability, this could include information on system components, KPIs, environmental factors, and historical data.
- **Output:** The output comprises probabilistic assessments of the impact on resilience and sustainable KPIs. Bayesian Networks can help in understanding the likelihood of different outcomes based on the given input data.

Knowledge Graph

- **Role:** The Knowledge Graph serves as a graphical model for evaluating and predicting the cascading effects of threat and vulnerability scenarios.
- **Input:** It expects input data related to threat and vulnerability scenarios, including information on the entities involved, their relationships, and potential impacts.

- **Output:** The output consists of a visual representation of the interconnected knowledge about threat and vulnerability scenarios. This aids in understanding how events are linked and predicting the cascading effects within the system.

Dynamic Routing

- **Role:** Dynamic Routing is responsible for multi-criteria dynamic route planning of the vessel fleet.
- **Input:** It requires input data related to vessel locations, destination points, real-time conditions (such as weather and traffic), and any relevant criteria for route planning.
- **Output:** The output includes optimized routes for the vessel fleet based on dynamic conditions and multiple criteria. This information assists in efficient and adaptable navigation for the vessels.

Data connectors

The data connectors play a vital role within the overarching Digital Twin framework, serving as a conduit for seamless data exchange. They enable bidirectional connectivity through the southbound interface, allowing the digital twin to engage in a dynamic environment of data acquisition and provision. This connectivity plays a pivotal role in enhancing the digital twin's functionality and utility from both ends:

- **Acquiring Information:** Digital twins thrive on a constant influx of data to maintain a comprehensive understanding of their operational context. This involves acquiring data from various external actors, including:
 - **Transport Providers:** For instance, a digital twin dedicated to optimizing shipment logistics requires real-time data from transport providers. This data could encompass route information, schedules, available capacities, and current status updates. By accessing this information, the digital twin can make informed decisions, such as selecting the most efficient route or suggesting alternative routes in case of disruptions.
 - **Authorities:** Regulatory constraints, legal requirements, and safety guidelines are integral to many industries. Digital twins often need to acquire information from regulatory bodies and authorities to ensure compliance and safety. These data inputs enable the digital twin to adapt to changing regulations and operational guidelines seamlessly.
- **Providing Information:** Digital twins are not just data consumers but also serve as invaluable data sources. They can contribute significantly by providing rich insights, real-time updates, and data-driven recommendations to various stakeholders, including:
 - **Transport Service Providers:** A digital twin possesses the capability to analyze historical data, current conditions, and predictive models to generate valuable insights.

Transport service providers can benefit immensely from these insights, using them to optimize routes, enhance maintenance schedules, and improve overall operational efficiency. For example, a digital twin can suggest maintenance activities based on equipment health trends, helping providers reduce downtime and improve service quality.

- Decision-Makers: Beyond service providers, decision-makers within organizations can leverage the digital twin's analytical capabilities to make informed choices. The digital twin can provide forecasts of future states, identify potential bottlenecks, and recommend strategic actions to mitigate risks or seize opportunities.

Among the data connectors, the dataspace connector serves as the bridge between the digital twin and these external actors, ensuring a seamless flow of data that empowers the digital twin to make intelligent decisions, enhance operations, and adapt to ever-changing conditions. Its bidirectional connectivity fosters a symbiotic relationship where data acquisition and provision mutually reinforce the digital twin's effectiveness, ultimately benefiting the entire ecosystem of stakeholders. The implementation of the dataspace connector is based on the LDES protocol, as described in deliverable D3.1 - Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT) Dataspace and generic Digital Twin Architecture v1.

API gateway

The API gateway is part of the services supporting the deployed digital twin applications. Its main role is to publish, maintain and monitor the APIs allowing the access to the digital twin applications output. It acts as a middleware between the hosted applications and the external ones. It harmonizes the access to the digital twin applications APIs by handling all the requests from the user applications and forwarding them to the relevant digital twin applications which are free to have their specific API definition. The main advantage is that the updates on the DT application API do not impact the final users' access in terms of API endpoints. Additionally, coupled with the authentication and authorization module, the API gateway enhances the protection of the DT applications against cybersecurity threats.

The API gateway requires input from the digital twins in terms of API definition, and from the authentication and authorization building block regarding the authorization framework and protocol.

The API gateway provides indirect access to the digital twin applications API for the user applications allowing them to consume data and insights from the hosted digital twins.

Figure 7: API gateway

Authentication and authorization

The authentication and authorization building block is responsible for the identity and access management of the platform. It ensures that only authenticated and authorized users and applications have access to the protected resources. The authorization rules are configured by the platform administrator based on the requirements of the owners of the hosted digital twin applications. When implemented, this building block is used as the authorization server by the API gateway e.g., every time a request to access the exposed API is received, the API gateway delegates to the authentication and authorization building block the responsibility to decide if the requester should be allowed or not.

The authentication and authorization building block receives as input authorization configurations from the platform administrator and authorization requests from the API gateway for which it provides the responses in terms of authorization clearances.

Virtualisation infrastructure

The virtualisation infrastructure provides the virtualised computing and memory resources necessary for the digital twin components and the services to operate. It can be implemented as virtual machines in which the software packages are installed or as containerized environment. The virtualisation infrastructure is managed by the virtualisation infrastructure manager instructing the deployment of the virtualised resources prior the instantiation of the hosted applications and managing the low-level access to each of the virtual machines or the containers through IP address and ports configuration.

The virtualised resources need to be carefully dimensioned which requires input from the digital twin components developers and information from the services software specifications.

5.3.2 Management

DT host management

The DT host manager groups the entities allowing the management of the deployed resources, applications, and services on the platform. The DT host manager provides the platform administrator with the interface to configure the services (e.g., the authorization rules, the low-level access, etc.) and monitor the provisioned resources with the help of the virtualisation infrastructure manager.

Automated deployment is not part of the requirements for the current version of the platform but in case it is introduced in the future versions, the DT host manager will have the responsibility to manage the configuration and provisioning tasks using automation tools such as Ansible or Puppet.

Virtualisation infrastructure management

The virtualisation infrastructure manager is responsible for the allocation and the release of the virtualised compute and memory resources. It receives provision instructions from the DT host manager and instantiates the required resources. It also collects monitoring information making it available to the DT host manager and the platform administrator.

5.3.3 Applications

The applications refer to any software that relies on the platform's northbound interface to interact with the deployed applications and services to access data and insights when it comes to digital twin applications. The development and the hosting of the applications are out of the scope of the platform except the ReNEW DT platform user interface and the admin user interface which can be shipped by default as part of the platform.

ReNEW DT platform user interface

The ReNEW DT platform user interface is a specific user application made available to the project's stakeholders, especially the LL. It constitutes the entry point to the platform for the non-administrative users. It facilitates the access to the output from the hosted digital twin applications such as data or insights. It relies on the northbound interface to interact with the underlying applications and services. As the requirements for this application are not yet fully specified, a more detailed description will be provided in the next version of this document.

Admin user interface

The admin user interface is another specific application allowing the platform administrator to interact with the DT platform manager and the virtualisation infrastructure manager through the admin interface. It allows the platform administrator to input configurations and instruct management tasks using a graphical or textual user interface.

5.3.4 Data Sources

The hosted digital twin applications require access to data sources for their operation. The platform aims at facilitating the access to data through dedicated services (e.g., data connectors) and

dedicated interface (southbound interface). It is then important to identify the potential data sources for the ReNEW digital twins before the implementation of the platform.

The data sources including the ReNEW dataspace feed the digital twins with a diverse range of information such as sensor data and topological data, among others. These inputs are critical in empowering the digital twin with real-time, actionable information, thus enabling an accurate replication and comprehension of the physical system it represents. For instance, sensor data provides essential insights into the current condition and behavior of the physical entity. This information is crucial for understanding the dynamic aspects of the system. In contrast, topological data contributes to a more spatial understanding, playing a key role in the overall system's structure and layout.

The process of assimilating this varied data is what equips the digital twin with the intelligence necessary for its effective operation. It allows the system to offer a comprehensive and accurate representation of the real-world environment, thereby supporting a wide range of analytical and decision-making processes.

We can categorize the data into two distinct types: static and dynamic data. Each type has its own unique requirements for acquisition, and different implementation strategies should be adopted, even when they are hosted within the same component.

Static data

Static data in the context of a digital twin for inland waterways primarily consists of information that does not frequently change over time. This includes, but is not limited to, geographical locations of infrastructures and details contained in vessel registries. This type of data establishes the fundamental base of knowledge for the digital twin, enabling it to comprehend and effectively operate within its designated environment. As of the time of this report, the integration of these static data sources is underway, contributing significantly to the overall functionality and accuracy of the digital twin system.

Static data, characterized by infrequent changes, forms the backbone of our digital twin system's operational context. The implementation strategy focuses on an internal storage mechanism that efficiently loads this data initially, followed by a periodic review for any updates. This approach ensures that the system is always operating with the most current and relevant static information. To optimize performance, data that is accessed frequently is cached internally, facilitating quicker retrieval, and reducing latency in system responses. The system's design also includes a configurable verification frequency for data updates. This flexibility allows us to tailor the update checks to match the anticipated rate of change in each specific data type. By adjusting these parameters, we can balance the need for up-to-date information with resource efficiency, ensuring the digital twin remains both accurate and agile in representing the real-world environment.

Dynamic Data

Dynamic data sources for the digital twin system encompass information that undergoes frequent changes and provides real-time insights into the current state of the waterway and its associated operations. These dynamic data sources play a crucial role in enhancing the system's ability to adapt, respond, and make informed decisions in real-time.

Dynamic data sources include, but are not limited to:

- Weather and Environmental Data: Real-time weather conditions, water levels, and other environmental factors are essential for understanding the immediate impact on waterway operations. This data helps the digital twin anticipate weather-related disruptions, optimize vessel routes, and ensure safety.
- Vessel Tracking and AIS Data: Automatic Identification System (AIS) data provides live updates on vessel positions, speeds, and courses. Integrating this data enables the digital twin to monitor vessel traffic, predict potential congestion points, and assist in collision avoidance. Data can be also utilized for trajectory and other data mining purposes.
- Traffic Management and Port Operations: Information regarding port activities, lock schedules, and traffic management protocols is vital for ensuring efficient navigation and minimizing delays. Dynamic data sources in this category help the digital twin coordinate vessel movements in real-time.
- Waterway Sensors: Sensors placed strategically along the waterway can provide real-time data on water quality, depth, and flow rates. This information assists in assessing the suitability of the route for vessels, especially during adverse conditions or for oversized cargo.
- Operational Logs and Maintenance Records: Maintenance data for locks, bridges, and other infrastructure components are dynamic in nature. Regular updates on maintenance schedules, ongoing work, and potential closures help the digital twin plan routes and avoid disruptions.
- Ship performance Data : speed, energy, carrying capacity vs draught, etc..

For the integration of the dynamic data sources, it must be considered the prioritization of real-time data retrieval, processing, and analysis. To achieve this, the digital twin system employs continuous data streaming and processing techniques.

Implementation strategy

A cohesive and unified approach is adopted for managing both static and dynamic data within the digital twin platform framework thanks to the data connectors. This approach leverages descriptive languages to precisely specify data sources, communication protocols (including REST API, MQTT, GraphQL, Webhooks, and HTTP), and connection properties. Components tailored to each protocol are initialized and configured to collect the necessary data according to predefined schedules and parameters described within the markup.

The foundation of this implementation strategy lies in the use of descriptive languages to articulate the various data sources. These descriptions not only detail the types of data available but also specify how the data should be accessed and under what conditions. This ensures a clear and standardized understanding of the information landscape, promoting interoperability and consistency.

The choice of communication protocols plays a critical role in enabling seamless data exchange between the digital twin and external entities. REST API, MQTT, GraphQL, Webhooks, and HTTP are carefully selected and configured based on the specific requirements of each data source. These protocols facilitate efficient and reliable data retrieval, allowing the digital twin to stay synchronized with its environment.

Connection properties, such as authentication mechanisms, encryption protocols, and data transmission formats, are meticulously defined within the descriptive language. These properties ensure secure and reliable data transfer, safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of the information exchanged.

To maintain data accuracy and relevance, the implementation strategy incorporates predefined schedules for data collection and ingestion. The descriptive language specifies when and how often data should be retrieved from various sources. This approach ensures that the digital twin operates with the most current and up-to-date information, enhancing its effectiveness in real-time decision-making.

Data ingestion into the digital twin platform is orchestrated through a messaging system. This system acts as a central hub for receiving and processing data from diverse sources. It facilitates efficient data routing, transformation, and storage, streamlining the integration of information into the digital twin's knowledge base. Within the messaging system, information is organized into distinct topics, each serving as a designated channel for a specific category of data. This organizational structure enhances the clarity and prioritization of incoming data. It allows the digital twin to efficiently manage and act upon different types of information, optimizing its responsiveness to changing conditions.

In summary, the implementation strategy for managing both static and dynamic data sources within the digital twin ecosystem relies on the precision of descriptive languages to define data sources, communication protocols, and connection properties. Scheduled data collection, coupled with a messaging system and topic-based organization, ensures the digital twin's ability to maintain an accurate and current representation of its environment, supporting its mission-critical functions.

5.4 Interfaces

The reference architecture in Figure 5 identifies 3 types of interfaces for the data exchange between the platform components and external entities such as applications and data sources.

5.4.1 Northbound Interface

The northbound interface allows the interaction between the user applications and the hosted digital twins. It is exposed by the API gateway which is responsible for handling all the requests coming from the user applications and forwarding them to the appropriate digital twin applications. Hence, the implementation of this interface is influenced by the way the digital twin applications are exposing their own interfaces. The access to the northbound interface is controlled by the API gateway with the support of the authentication and authorization building block when it comes to the authorization rules. The endpoints such as the IP address and the ports are managed by the DT host manager.

5.4.2 Southbound Interface

The southbound interface is dedicated to the interaction between the digital twin applications and the data sources from which they get the data they need to operate. This interface is configured based on the requirements from the digital twin applications but also the data sources that need to be reached for. The endpoints such as the IP address and the ports are managed by the DT host manager.

5.4.3 Admin Interface

The admin interface allows the admin users of the platform to interact with the DT host manager and the virtualisation infrastructure manager. In its simple implementation, it corresponds to the interfaces exposed by these two building blocks usually accessible via API. The admin interface access is protected using either dedicated access control features in the DT host manager solution or the authentication and authorisation building block of the platform.

5.5 Technical Implementation Recommendations

This section describes the implementation of the ReNEW digital twin platform architecture with a selection of tools and technical solutions. They have been chosen by taking into account the requirements but also the known technical solutions retained for the digital twin development as well as the data sources specifications. Additionally, open-source solutions are preferred and prioritized as much as possible.

5.5.1 Cloud computing and Microsoft Azure

Edge computing and cloud computing are two different approaches to data processing that can be used together to achieve optimal performance. Cloud computing provides scalable computing and storage resources and is used to run workloads within clouds. Edge computing, on the other hand, involves running workloads on edge devices that are at or near the physical location of either the user or the source of the data. Edge computing is particularly useful for processing delay-sensitive and bandwidth-hungry applications near the data source by pre-processing data. The right combination of cloud and edge-based applications is key to achieving maximum performance.

Cloud computing platform can create and launch applications more quickly, while also ensuring that the apps can be updated and changed in response to the needs. This means that partners can keep their apps up to date for a longer period of time.

Principal benefits of the cloud computing platform and Azure are:

- scalability and flexibility as it allows businesses to adjust their computing resources easily, according to their changing needs. As a result, businesses don't need to invest in additional infrastructure and can adapt to new requirements more easily.
- assisting businesses in reducing their IT infrastructure expenses. This is achieved through the pay-as-you-go model offered by main cloud providers, which allows businesses to avoid costly investments in hardware and software. By using the pay-as-you-go model, businesses are only charged based on the resources they use, which makes it an affordable solution.
- providing a range of security services, including encryption and multi-factor authentication, to ensure the safety of businesses' data and applications in the cloud.
- providing a user-friendly tool for easy cloud application development, testing, and deployment.
- offering a variety of machine learning and AI services that enable users to extract valuable insights from data. These services can be utilized to develop predictive models, execute natural language processing, and automate routine tasks.

Microsoft Azure is a platform and service for cloud computing that provides an extensive array of computing resources and services, including computing power, storage, analytics, and networking. Also, Azure can be easily integrated with other Microsoft services such as Office 365, Dynamics 365, and Power BI, providing comprehensive tools for businesses to streamline their operations.

As part of the partnership with Microsoft, we at AKKODIS have expertise in deploying systems under AZURE associated with API gateways such as APISIX and Keycloak authentication building block.

5.5.2 Keycloak

Keycloak is an open-source Identity and Access Management solution that allows you to add authentication to your applications and secure services with minimal effort. Keycloak provides both SAML (Security Assertion Markup Language) and OpenID protocol solutions as they are industry standards. Building an application that is integrated with Keycloak will provide a more secure and stable solution. Some benefits of Keycloak:

- Keycloak is a fast and flexible solution that keeps up with the constant evolution of new standards, technologies, and functional requirements. Its community is quick to adapt to these changes, as demonstrated by the recent migration to the Quarkus (Java for the cloud) runtime. The solution is designed to be agile and is suited for fast-changing application landscapes. It offers high stability and can scale up to meet the needs of large organizations.

- Open-Source Software (OSS) is free to use, as it does not require a license or service fee. The source code is available for anyone to access without any restrictions. Being an open-source software, it allows for adjustments and modifications to be made by anyone, anytime. Additionally, there is no vendor lock-in, which means it's cost-effective, robust, and continuously maintained.
- A large global community of contributors and users provides Keycloak with quick feedback and advice. Red Hat, the primary contributor, supports Keycloak as RH-SSO in their product suites.
- Authorization & Authentication: This feature allows for easy addition of authentication to applications and security services. Users can log in to the system using a single account or virtual identity, without the need to store or authenticate users manually.
- System administration will seamlessly manage user accounts, maintain data, and sessions.
- It can be utilized either as an element of an IT infrastructure or a standalone solution.

OIDC is a centralized identity authentication mode. The benefit of using OIDC is that users only need to register and log in with one OIDC identity provider's website like Keycloak and use one account's password information to access different applications. OIDC Plug-in for Apache APISIX supports OIDC to simplify the development process and improve security at the API Gateway level. It alone interacts with the identity provider and can intercept unauthenticated requests in time to back-end applications.

5.5.3 Apache APISIX

Apache APISIX is a lightweight open-source API gateway that sits in front of upstream services. Easy to configure and quick to deploy, APISIX API Gateway serves as a central point for routing all incoming requests to their intended destinations, whether that be an upstream API server, a third-party service, a database, or even a serverless. The API gateway comes with numerous built-in plugins to manage authentication, authorization, traffic control, and security. Our selected plugin is APISIX OpenID Connect (OIDC).

Here are some principal benefits of choosing APISIX:

- The open-source license is the most crucial factor to consider when choosing an open-source API gateway.
- API and API gateway are popular among software engineers, who are both users and developers. This popularity serves as an indicator of current trends.
- Apache APISIX simplifies management and scaling of API, allowing for handling of increased traffic and usage demands.
- Apache APISIX can improve API performance by caching responses and reducing latency.
- Apache APISIX offers encryption and authentication for secure access to API.
- Apache APISIX offers a flexible way to manage and control access to the API. This allows users to customize and configure their integration as required.

- Apache APISIX offers detailed monitoring and analytics to help optimize API integration performance.

APISIX-Keycloak exchange flow

When using the APISIX OIDC plugin together with an identity provider (IDP) (in our case Keycloak), the authentication flow is commonly divided into 3 stages, **sign-in**, **access**, and **session** flow:

- Sign in flow:
 1. The client service requests access to the APISIX API gateway.
 2. APISIX initiates an authentication (auth cookie) by redirecting the client request to the Identity Provider, in our case it is Keycloak.
 3. The user logs in and authenticates on the Keycloak.
 4. The Keycloak IDP returns to APISIX API Gateway with the Authorization Code and redirects the client request back to APISIX.

As you can see from the diagram, APISIX does not allow unauthenticated requests to pass to upstream services (backend services).

- Access flow
 5. APISIX requests the identity provider (auth code and auth cookie) with
 6. the Authorization Code extracted from the request parameters in the previous flow.
 7. The IDP sends an answer message to APISIX with the Access Token.
 8. After validating the token (access token), finally, by
 9. Getting the service response from OIDC
 10. APISIX sends user info to upstream services. Inside services only accept connections from API Gateway (session code).
- Session flow: Up to now, authentication has already happened, and in the later stages,
 11. The client application can request directly (auth cookie) APISIX without duplicative verification.
 12. However, upstream services should be able to handle custom headers with user info.
 13. And APISIX get service responses.
 14. Finally, APISIX sends to client service response along with (session cookie).

Figure 8: APISIX -Keycloak exchange flow

5.5.4 Digital Twin Platform Deployment on Azure

Figure 9 indicates a mapping between the reference architecture and the retained technical solutions.

In our case, Azure Cloud Services is used as an Infrastructure-As-A-Service provider. As such the virtualisation infrastructure and its management is handled by Azure through its proprietary hypervisor. The platform administrator only gives provisioning instructions through a command line interface (Azure CLI) or a graphical user interface (Azure portal) implementing the Admin UI. Then the hypervisor takes care of the instantiation of the requested compute memory and network resources. As a result, Virtual Machines (VMs) are available to host the digital twin applications and the services.

Apache APISIX has been retained to implement the API gateway building block:

- The APISIX routes will refer to the harmonized API to be used by any external applications to reach the digital twin applications. Hence, they will implement the northbound interface of the platform.
- The APISIX upstreams will refer to the digital twin applications which are the provider of the specific API from which data and insights are provided
- The APISIX admin API will be available as part of the admin interface
- The APISIX dashboard will be also accessible as part of the admin UI
- The APISIX openid-connect plugin will be used to facilitate the integration with Keycloak managing the authentication and authorisation aspects.

Keycloak has been chosen to act as the authentication and authorisation server in the platform implementing the authentication and authorization building block:

- The Keycloak admin API will be part of the admin interface of the platform

The Keycloak admin console will be available as part of the admin UI allowing the configuration of the authorization rules.

Figure 9: ReNEW digital twin platform implementation

6 Deployment

This section focuses on the planned deployment of the initial version of the ReNEW digital twin platform and the general steps to be followed to host a digital twin application.

6.1 Instantiating the ReNEW Digital Twin Platform

Figure 10 shows the deployment template to be followed when instantiating the digital twin platform. It corresponds to the deployment state to be reached to ensure an operational deployment of the platform.

Figure 10: ReNEW digital twin platform deployment

Using the Azure Portal, a web application accessible from the Internet acting as the Admin UI, the ReNEW Digital Twin Platform administrator instantiates two groups of virtual machines:

- The services VM to host the services applications. In the current version of the platform, 3 VMs are envisaged to deploy the API gateway (APISIX), the authentication and authorisation module (Keycloak) and the data connectors
- The DT VM to host the digital twin components. The total number of VMs in this group depends on the digital twin applications developers' requirements

The VMs inside each group share a virtual network allowing communication between them if necessary. The two VM groups are interfaced with each other allowing the DT VMs to reach the deployed services. Only the services VM have direct access to Internet. Nevertheless, direct admin access like SSH to the DT VMs can be granted by the platform admin to the digital twin developers through the Azure Portal.

Once the VMs are instantiated, the platform admin deploys the services software on the corresponding VMs. For each service, the platform admin set up the necessary access configuration on the hosting VM including the ports to be opened and the DNS.

After the services deployment, the digital twin developers are provided admin access to their hosting VMs in order to deploy the digital twin core components. They are also provided with the services access details such as private IP addresses and ports.

Once the digital twin core components are up and running, additional configuration needs to be performed at the API gateway to define the routes from the exposed APIs towards the internal digital twin applications APIs allowing the user applications from the Internet to access them.

A sequence diagram illustrating the main steps to be followed to instantiate the ReNEW digital twin platform is presented in Figure 11 with the platform administrator as the main actor interacting with the Azure Portal and the services VMs.

Figure 11: ReNEW digital twin platform instantiation

6.2 Hosting a Digital Twin Application

Figure 12 shows a sequence diagram highlighting the steps to be followed to host a digital twin application on the platform. The prerequisite is that the ReNEW digital twin platform is correctly instantiated and configured with the services up and running.

It starts with the digital twin developer providing their resource requirements to the platform admin. They include the needs in terms of computing, memory, and network resources for the digital twin application to be operational once deployed. The platform admin takes them into consideration to instantiate the necessary VMs on which the digital twin application components will be deployed. Then the platform admin provides the developer with a remote access to the instantiated digital twin VMs. Additionally, the developer receives all the technical information regarding the access to the available services such as the internal IP address and ports and any required configuration on the application side.

The digital twin application developer continues with the installation and configuration of the digital twin components directly on the provided VMs. Afterwards, the developer indicates the requirements from the deployed application in terms of services including the exposed API, the resources to be protected behind authentication and authorisation, etc.

Finally, the platform admin considers the provided service requirements to configure the deployed services on the platform allowing the hosted digital twin application to integrate with them. At this point, the digital twin application is operational and available to the authorised user applications.

Hosting a digital twin application

Figure 12: Digital twin application deployment on the platform

6.3 Digital Twin Deployment Schedule

With the help of WP3 partners steps and timeframe were identified to produce a retro planning of the Digital Twin platform deployment steps. Figure 13 shows an estimated timetable for the steps to be taken before the first LL deployment.

Figure 13: Digital twin platform deployment planning

7 Conclusion and Recommendation

The purpose of this proposition is to present the technical choices and deployment strategy. We also make some recommendations about the tools and applications that will be used.

The implementation of demonstrated solutions will occur in the Living Labs, with support and guidance from the DT and data spaces team. The task will continually refine and update the DT and data spaces based on the needs of the Living Lab stakeholders.

The partners of WP3 have identified 17 requirements for a seamless integration and deployment of the DT. Among them, 8 are categorized as IWT digital twin, 4 as software requirements, 3 as data access requirements, 1 as a security requirement, and 1 as a UI requirement. Additionally, there are 11 DS requirements, 6 of them are mandatory. We also identified 8 functional requirements, 4 interface requirements, and the others are shared between management, provisioning, and security requirements. Furthermore, there are 7 different non-functional requirements.

To replicate the physical system accurately, the ReNEW digital twin platform needs to integrate diverse data sources, establish robust communication, and implement an API gateway, authentication/authorization, scheduled data collection, messaging systems, and topic-based organization. The ReNEW digital twin platform relies on specialized services and interfaces to gather data from multiple sources. The data connector, linked to the southbound interface, provides access to sensor and topological data for real-time insights. Sensor data reveals the physical entity's current condition and behavior, while topological data contributes to a spatial understanding of the system.

To deploy the digital twin platform, we recommend using Cloud Services offering the necessary virtualization infrastructure and management capabilities required for the deployment. Additionally, Keycloak can be leveraged for authentication purposes in the platform, ensuring secure and reliable access for users. For handling client application requests and providing service responses, Apache APISIX can be used to streamline communication between client applications and upstream services.

It is recommended to deploy Digital Twins (DTs) that are customized for the resilient and sustainable IWT infrastructure system. Guidelines for deploying DTs should be developed, taking into account their integration into the decision-making process, the current state of the system, and the evaluation of performance indicators. Quantification services for resilience and sustainability should be launched and deployed in Living Labs. A comprehensive system representation should be facilitated and developed, which allows for benchmarking of service levels, considering the positive correlation between resilience and sustainability.

8 References

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